

Assessing teacher's support during the extensive reading literacy program of Brigada Pagbasa at Landy National High School

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Abstract

Reading literacy is needed to become a good reader and is essential for knowledge acquisition and global comprehension. The government, organizations, citizens, and especially teachers in the Philippines support initiatives to improve literacy. The literacy style observed in the respondent's school varies depending on experience, knowledge status, and educational background (Idulog et al., 2023). This study focuses on how teachers assess and support students regarding extensive reading literacy. This study sought to understand the teachers' techniques when assessing the extensive reading literacy program and how these techniques improve the students. Five junior high school students were the participants of this study. The researcher used a questionnaire with ten semi-structured interview questions. Teachers' guidance and assistance are essential for many students because they play a significant role in developing their skills and giving them more knowledge about extensive literacy. Teachers guide the students in improving their reading and language skills regarding practical communication skills. Providing the students with more books and teaching them to do repetitive reading will enhance their reading skills, and the teacher's support will positively impact them (Yang et al., 2021). Overall, it can be concluded from the text that extended reading programs are successful when teachers provide students with directional assistance and access to various reading materials. Despite obstacles, students embrace the advantages of in-depth reading and appreciate its influence on their academic and personal development.

Keywords: Brigada Pagbasa; Extensive Reading; Teachers; Students; Reading program.

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Introduction

Early book exposure and proficient reading comprehension skills increase a child's chances of learning language as opposed to non-readers or inexperienced readers. Their language and reading comprehension may be affected by reading. Children's reading comprehension and fluency increase the knowledge they consume. Therefore, reading allows children to develop their cognitive and linguistic skills. Thus, instructing students is a teacher's primary responsibility, as is reading to the class. All students' future success unquestionably depends on their ability to learn to read effectively in the modern world.

Based on Department of Education (DepEd) Memorandum No. 048 s. 2021, issued August 2, 2021, as part of Brigada Eskwela, the Brigada Pagbasa is an after-school reading project that aims to unite professionals and education partners to support all students in reading and developing functional literacy (Briones, 2021). The Brigada Pagbasa will act as the center for tackling educational difficulties, mainly those related to reading and numeracy, by merging resources and exerting effort. It will also afford all concerned parties the opportunity to contemplate potential solutions for the current shortcomings in the country's educational system, particularly in relation to 21st-century skills.

The Division Partnership Focal Persons are urged to inventory school reading initiatives that have partnership components and could be included in Brigada Pagbasa prior to the program's creation. Brigada Pagbasa's implementation guidelines in detail will be given in a separate release (Llego, 2022). Reading is the process of interpreting written or printed material with many different elements. The five basic components of reading are comprehension, vocabulary, pronunciation, fluency, and listening comprehension. Reading is both a tool for education and one of life's essential skills. It is the foundation for prosperity and personal growth and encourages people to look for the purpose of life. Most learning requires reading, and as students move up the educational ladder, reading goes becoming increasingly vital.

According to Valisno (2010), in a memorandum on the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory, people improve the efficiency of their reading skills by applying their knowledge and skills to their primary grades, future courses, and professions. Reading is a fundamental talent associated with other abilities, including writing, speaking, and listening. It can be used to teach students how to extract information from texts and create interpretations of them. A student who enjoys reading and engages in reading activities frequently can write effectively. A competent instructor should be adept at interpreting grammar and terminology. The objective of teaching reading is to develop students' literacy skills, including their capacity to read various English-language texts, adapt their reading habits to the purpose of their reading, and form an informed opinion on the text's subject matter.

Accurate reading requires knowledge of prior literature and the ability to comprehend the author's writing. While some readers realize the book by putting together its concepts with their prior knowledge and experiences, others deduce meaning from the text. The ability to interact with and employ knowledge contained in a text in an efficient manner is known as reading comprehension. Many people who read the content could find themselves repeating difficult sentences even though they can understand it word for word. It is determined by ability and disposition and can improve vocabulary and writing competence.

Teachers help children develop reading habits and interests. They provide a structured and dynamic learning environment, base their classroom activities on reliable reading theory, employ various instructional methods, and routinely evaluate their students' reading proficiency. This has a positive impact on the achievement of their pupils. Motivated readers read more, employ more basic learning techniques, and improve as readers. Teachers must tailor their lessons to match their students' present reading development.

Teachers should use class time better, maximize resources, and lead instruction for large and small groups. Their expectations of and interactions with their students significantly impact their learning. Students' knowledge, experiences, and interests are expanded, and they are more likely to achieve academically when they feel appreciated, accepted, and provided with difficult resources. The top reading educators place a high value on growing both individually and together as professionals. Through peer coaching, mentorships, professional reading clubs, networking events with peers, and literacy workshops and conferences, they look for opportunities to learn more. Additionally, they take advantage of professional development opportunities to broaden their expertise across all topic areas.

In a press release issued by the Senate of the Philippines in 2022, Senator Sherwin Gatchalian stated that many assessments revealed how challenging it was for kids to attain a minimal level of reading competency. Reading is one of the pillars that needs to be reinforced for the younger generation. Since the pandemic started, education has been greatly impacted, making it more important than ever for the government to prioritize. Reading is one of the main areas of educational deficiency in which the Department of Education strives for achievement. Gatchalian has a campaign where parents and instructors play essential responsibilities in ensuring that students can comprehend and read what they are reading in order for them to succeed.

The researcher was motivated to conduct an assessment of teacher support during the extensive reading literacy program of Brigada Pagbasa at Landy National High School to be able to assess how the teacher supports the students in extensive reading literacy, the reasons why the students seek teacher support during extensive reading literacy, and the importance of extensive reading literacy.

General Objectives

The researcher wants to know why the selected students seek support during extensive reading literacy and why the selected students of Landy National High School have slow growth in reading literacy.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher aims to know the importance of assessing teacher support during the ready literacy in Brigada Pagbasa at Landy National High School. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following:

1. How does teacher support the students in extensive reading literacy?
2. Why do the students seek teacher support during extensive reading literacy?
3. What is the importance of an extensive reading literacy program on the selected Landy National High School students?

This study aimed to investigate how the teachers supported the selected Landy National High School students during the extensive Brigada Pagbasa literacy program. This study used a qualitative phenomenological study approach, including five junior high school students from Landy National High School in Santa Cruz, Marinduque, Philippines. This study was conducted during the school year 2023-2024 and limited only to the feedback of the selected junior high school students. The study looked at the teacher's assistance with the pupils' comprehensive reading literacy curriculum. In order to verify Landy National High School's extensive reading literacy curriculum, the researcher observes how beneficial extensive reading literacy is to the students.

The study aims to determine the effectiveness of the extensive reading literacy program for the selected students. The researcher believes that extensive reading literacy is very practical and helpful to the students and helps them improve their reading comprehension. Extensive reading helps teachers be better informed about their profession, the world of reading, and its importance. Through this study, professionals like teachers can determine the effectiveness of reading and how they will assess learners. Reading a lot has several benefits for learning a language. Improved vocabulary, written and verbal communication skills, reading and writing competency, drive, self-worth, and empathy are a few of these. Students who read widely also acquire outstanding skills for independent learning. The study's findings may help the school administration create more programs about extensive reading literacy to increase students' development in reading literacy. Programs and learning hubs will benefit the learners by providing quality reading time.

Literature Review

Extensive Reading Literacy

According to Bamford and Day (1997), pioneers like Harold Palmer in Britain and Michael West in India developed the theory and methods of extensive reading as a way to teach foreign languages generally and the skill of reading in those languages. Palmer specifically used the term "extensive reading" to set it apart from "intensive reading." Intensive reading corresponds to the deliberate reading of shorter, harder foreign language texts with the aim of thorough comprehension. Both forms of reading have academic value and can be seen in terms of objectives or results.

Cassidy and Ortlieb (2013) stated that reading research and practice have always placed a strong emphasis on comprehension training and instruction, which has been largely disregarded in favor of problems with beginning reading, phonics, and decoding during the past few decades. But lately, comprehension training has received more attention, especially in the federal sphere.

Griffin et al. (1998) discussed that under the Reading Excellence Act, reading and teaching comprehension are still confusing for teachers. When we inquire about their work, they discover that they are constantly seeking new concepts and more specific methods to enhance their students' understanding abilities, even when employing a program for essential reading adopted by the district. Teachers ask, "What is the greatest way to teach? Where can I get a comprehension program that is based on research? How about my kids, who are proficient readers but lack comprehension of what they read? What can I do to assist my hesitant readers?" There are several research-based educational paradigms that teachers can employ to raise the comprehension levels of their students. The issue is that many educators are not aware of these frameworks for teaching understanding.

Teachers must pay more attention to developing effective educational strategies that facilitate children's acquisition of these skills. Regarding metacognition, recognizing the structure of graphics and the structure of text and stories is one of the most effective strategies for improving reading comprehension. Giving learners several readings of the same material will boost their confidence in addition to helping them become proficient. A person's likelihood of enjoying reading increases with his or her level of confidence in the reading abilities.

Challenges

According to Carrell and Carson (1997), "extensive reading... generally involves rapid reading of large quantities of material or longer readings (e.g., whole books) for general understanding, with the focus generally on the meaning of what is being read (rather) than on the language." From the perspective of classroom implementation, Davis (1995) provides a more useful description, even though this one gives an overview of extensive reading.

An extensive reading program is an additional class library plan related to an English course in which students are provided with the time, resources, and support to read as many books as they can for enjoyment, at their reading level, and without the burden of grades or tests. Students therefore only compete against themselves, and it is the teacher's responsibility to inspire them and keep an eye on them to make sure they read the most books in the allotted time. Books are chosen more for their aesthetic appeal and practicality in the lives of the students than for their literary value because quantity and variety are the guiding principles rather than quality. A child's inability to read can be attributed to a number of issues, such as inadequate book exposure, problems with speech and hearing, and a deficiency in phonemic awareness.

Challenges in any of these domains can hinder the progress of reading skills. Additionally, acquiring reading skills begins well before children begin their formal education. Children exposed to enriching literary encounters from infancy possess an advantage in building their vocabulary, comprehending reading objectives, and cultivating an understanding of print and literary principles.

Difficulties

Many teachers may not have the tools needed to cope with the needs of students who require the most extensive reading support (McMaster et al., 2021). The purpose of this analysis was to ascertain the ways in which researchers have provided professional development (PD) to support educators in implementing intensive reading measures, the extent to which these approaches incorporate essential PD components, and the methods by which researchers have evaluated implementer outcomes in the 26 trials under review. Of the 26 trials that were reviewed, the majority received initial training and ongoing support. Most studies appeared to include one or more crucial PD components; however, many lacked sufficient information on their presence. Implementer outcomes were often evaluated using various fidelity measures and other techniques.

Based on the articles, it is concluded that the involvement of teachers in extensive reading is very important in improving the students' reading skills. The researcher determines how important it is to improve the student's skills in extensive reading, what difficulties they experience, and what strategies are used to improve their reading ability. The researcher also presents the related literature about the topic and provides further information driving the given timetable.

Methodology

The researcher utilized a qualitative approach to gather information for this study. Qualitative research allows one to explore and understand survey respondents' unique insights and experiences. As Shank (2005) noted, qualitative research aims to examine meaning, which involves understanding the essence of human experiences and their importance to their lives. The qualitative approach was used in this study since it dealt with complex issues requiring an in-depth understanding of people's experiences and perspectives. Qualitative data for this study were derived from transcriptions of interviews and observations. The researcher obtained rich and extensive information about the respondents' opinions, attitudes, beliefs, and experiences and how the teacher supported the students in their extensive reading literacy program through observations and interviews.

This study was conducted at Landy National High School in the Santa Cruz North District of Santa Cruz, Province of Marinduque, Philippines. This locale was chosen because all schools are implementing Brigada Pagbasa, wherein part of the educational program is to enhance the reading capability of the students. Furthermore, the location was chosen considering how well it would represent the entire institution's population since the respondents were purposefully chosen.

This study utilized selective sampling to identify how the teacher supported the students in their extensive reading literacy program. The research participants are five junior high school students from Landy National High School. During the Brigada Pagbasa, the participants carefully determined how the teacher supported the students in their extensive reading literacy program.

This study focuses on the students who participated in the extensive reading program, which includes five students from junior high school studying at Landy National High School in Santa Cruz, Marinduque. The researcher chose only five students who were suitable for the study.

Five students have questions to answer by interview, and they are free to respond based on their thoughts and experiences about extensive reading. Giving them much time to think and review their experience to comfortably answer the question.

Semi-structured interview questions are used in this study as a suitable tool to collect information regarding the participants' experiences with alienation. Open-ended questions were used in the semi-structured interview to allow participants to delve deeply into the subject while maintaining flexibility to elicit more thorough answers. Another method to gather data involves paying close attention through observational techniques and meticulously collecting pertinent and precise information. This meticulous approach determines how the teacher supports the students in their extensive reading literacy program.

After gathering data from the detailed observations and insightful interviews conducted, the collected data underwent an immediate and thorough analysis and evaluation. This essential step in the research procedure is designed to meticulously scrutinize and interpret the data, guaranteeing that the final results are firmly grounded in precise and pertinent information, ensuring the validity and reliability of the research findings.

During the initial stage of the systematic process, the participants' responses and observations are meticulously transcribed into written formats. This crucial stage allowed for a thorough examination of every transcript, allowing for an in-depth investigation of the data and a profound comprehension of its findings. These tools and methods for gathering data were ideal for addressing the objectives and research questions. It allowed the collection of rich and comprehensive data to determine how the teacher supported the students in their extensive reading literacy program.

However, before the study was conducted, it was of utmost importance to provide each participant with a comprehensive understanding of the significance of their involvement. The respondents must have assurance regarding the importance and value of what they have to contribute to the research. They are also guaranteed that strong confidentiality protocols will be used for any information they share. Participants can feel assured in the knowledge that the information gathered will only be used to further the research and expand knowledge in the particular subject of study.

The researcher's face-to-face interview occurred on Thursday and Friday, May 4 to 5, from 11:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m. At 11:45 am, various conversations between the teachers and learners were observed about the techniques used by the teachers and how effective they are. Sometimes, the book they read is difficult, so the teachers teach them some words they cannot read properly. To gather more information on the practical support of the teachers through extensive reading, the researcher returned to the respondents after lunch and asked the questions (Parrish, 2020).

Ethical Considerations

The researcher first asked the School Head's permission to conduct the study. After obtaining the consent of the School Head, the researcher met the participants and informed them about the study, how their participation was needed, and how they would be observed. It is conducted while following ethical considerations when conducting research. The data gathered was analyzed and processed after obtaining statements regarding the phenomenon.

The researcher asked the same set of questions during the interview. Due to the intense heat in the province, which forced the Department of Education to change class schedules, the study was conducted entirely online via video calls and other online platforms, making it more challenging to interact directly with study participants. Additionally, for their privacy, they were informed that the conversation will be recorded throughout, so it will be officially documented. It utilized ten semi-structured questionnaires to conduct the interview and collect participant data.

Results

Conversation Between Teachers and Learners

While observing, the researcher noticed that the teachers and their students engaged in various conversations related to literacy practices. Some of these conversations were simple, such as parents asking about their children's schoolwork or children discussing their own experiences.

Style of Literacy

Based on the experience, level of knowledge, and educational background of the respondents, different literacy styles are seen in their school. It appears that a student's literacy style affects their reading proficiency and practices. For instance, we can argue that the respondent learns something from our daily reading and becomes better at school by focusing more on reading. The teacher supports their students in improving their reading to understand the situation carefully. Sometimes we need time to read, such as going to the library and getting a book and reading it.

In contrast, the students do not have enough time to read because of the mobile games. Instead of going to the library, they want to stay in the classroom and play games on their cell phones. The students did not wish for any improvement to show how to improve their language skills. Overall, the literacy style observed in the respondents' school was influenced by their experience, educational background, cultural values, and student literacy practices; whether reading or writing directly or not, it impacted their knowledge.

Table 1 displays the teachers' importance and guidance in extensive reading. The importance of extensive reading is categorized into four elements: an effective way of teaching, teacher guidance, the effect of the reading program, and the impact of the reading program. Teachers' guidance and assistance are essential for many students because they play a significant role in developing their skills and giving them more knowledge about extensive literacy.

Teachers' guidance and assistance are essential for many students because they play a significant role in developing their skills and giving them more knowledge about extensive literacy. Teachers guide the students in improving their reading and language skills regarding practical communication skills. Many respondents said that giving the students more books to read and making them read over and over again will improve their reading skills, and the teacher's support will positively impact them.

Table 1. Teacher's support in extensive reading literacy

Theme	Categories	Thematic statement
Teacher's support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An effective way of teaching Techniques Individual needs 	<i>R1. One of the most effective ways for teachers to support their students in reading growth is to focus on the individual needs of each student and to have an extensive collection of books and other materials for reading in the classroom.</i>
Assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidance Teaching support 	<i>R2. Guide the children properly and teach them in a good way.</i>
Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact of reading Positive knowledge 	<i>R3. Wide reading and literacy have a positive impact on a student by expanding his knowledge and understanding of the world, strengthening his critical thinking, and expanding his imagination and ability to relate to others.</i>

One of the respondents said: "Wide reading and literacy have a positive impact on a student by expanding his knowledge and understanding of the world, strengthening his critical thinking, and expanding his imagination and ability to relate to others." In support of the claim above, according to Rao and Babu (2016), as cited by Taha and Al Sukhon (2023), there are numerous difficulties in teaching English. Teaching grammar and vocabulary are the two most important areas to focus on in every issue. Many studies have been conducted over the past two decades to provide efficient teaching methods and tools for language proficiency. The extensive reading approach is one of the most crucial strategies that many studies recommend using to increase language proficiency, including vocabulary and comprehension. An extensive reading program that is included in the curriculum may significantly improve students' capacity to pick up languages. The authors encourage teachers to utilize extensive reading as a tool to analyze their assumptions about reading in general, extensive reading in particular, and the manner in which learners gain very crucial language skills for the purpose of academic and professional development.

According to Ghafar (2023), a wide range of digital tools are being used to teach English as a second language to young students. Teachers need to be aware of how each student's needs are changing in order to deliver the best instruction. In addition, it makes sense that the possibility of problems makes the educational process difficult. Every challenge needs to be closely watched by an experienced teacher to avoid inhibiting learning.

Table 2. Students seeking support during extensive reading literacy program

Theme	Categories	Thematic statement
Guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share knowledge Support Inspire 	<i>R1. We need the teachers support while studying to guide us, inspire us, and share knowledge that will help us progress and succeed in education.</i>
Progression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Growth Individual Extensive 	<i>R2. One of the most effective ways for teachers to support their students in reading growth is to use a focus on the individual needs of each student and to have an extensive collection of books and other materials in reading in the classroom.</i>
Examination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation Literature Interest 	<i>R3. Teachers can strengthen students' motivation to judge during extensive reading of literature by providing lively discussions, allocating space for opinions and expressing ideas, and showing their own interest. and enjoyment of studying literature.</i>

Table 2 displays the many difficulties encountered during the extensive reading literacy program. These challenges were categorized into three: guide, progress, and examine. According to the information gathered and displayed in the table, respondents prioritize their own and their children's education; extensive reading is required despite challenges and confusion. The first statement emphasizes how crucial it is to provide guidance to someone who has to multitask, like a student. This indicates that the respondents are making a conscious effort to successfully balance their duties. The second statement demonstrates that respondents enjoy having old notes and books for reference. The third statement indicates that respondents are actively involved in some activity. The learning space challenge in this case is the lack of time and physical space to create a reading-friendly home environment. As a Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) student, he or she may have busy schedules and little time for leisure activities such as reading. This creates the challenge of finding the time and place to engage in reading and writing activities that support learning goals.

"In my opinion, it is easier to learn if the teacher is teaching because they have the experience, knowledge, and ability to express and guide you in understanding the concepts and importance of what is being taught."

"As a student, I can value the program of extensive reading in my daily studies by opening my mind and being open to new ideas, being active in the discussion and contributing my own point of view, and devoting time and effort to researching and doing literature-related tasks."

"When I share what I have learned about the program with my fellow students, I will describe it through familiar words and examples to make it easy to understand. I will argue the importance of the program, the benefits that can be obtained, and how it can help their development and success."

Based on the explanations given, it can be inferred that instruction could be a need for them, indeed, within the context of different challenges and disturbances in their day-to-day lives. They are taking steps to oversee their time viably, get significant assets, and create an environment conducive to learning and examining. The study showed that applying the extensive reading technique increased students' vocabularies. The children's vocabulary greatly improved as a result of receiving treatment employing an extensive reading method, according to the results. Reading extensively can help language learners in many ways, as previous studies have demonstrated.

According to Krashen (1989), reading a lot of literature helps enhance vocabulary growth, reading comprehension, and general language competence. Furthermore, Day et al. (1998) discovered that reading a lot can help children become more motivated to study and have better attitudes towards reading. Other research has examined the connection between reading a lot and developing particular language skills. According to Horst et al. (1998), it can improve students understanding of collocations. Despite these possible benefits, certain researchers have also identified drawbacks and difficulties related to extensive reading.

Not every student will benefit from it, and some might have to reach a certain skill level before they enjoy the benefits of reading a lot. Concerns have also been expressed over how challenging it can be to choose reading materials that are appropriate for students with varying competence levels.

Table 3. Importance of extensive reading literacy program on the selected students

Theme	Categories	Thematic statement
Enrichment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expanding vocabulary Understanding Critical Thinking 	<i>R3. The extensive reading programs affect the reading skills of the selected student by expanding their vocabulary improving their ability to understand and interpret text and strengthening their critical thinking and analysis of text.</i>
Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giving value Being active Devoting time 	<i>R4. As a student, I can value the program of extensive reading in my daily study by opening my mind and being open to the new ideas, being active in the discussion and contributing my own point to view and devoting time and effort to researching and doing.</i>
Empowering growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positive impact Strengthening Expanding imagination 	<i>R5. Wide reading and literacy have a positive impact on a student by expanding to the world. Strengthening his critical thinking and expanding his imagination and ability to relate to others.</i>
Progress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Importance Benefits Development 	<i>R1. When I share what I have learned about the program with my fellow students, I will describe it through familiar words and explain to make it easy to understand. I will argue the importance of the program, the benefits that can be obtained and how it can help the development and success.</i>

Table 3 shows that the comprehensive reading curriculum aims to significantly improve students' reading abilities. Students who read a lot gain a number of important advantages that support their general growth.

First, prolonged reading helps children's vocabulary grow. Students gradually expand their lexical vocabulary by coming across unexpected words and phrases through exposure to a variety of texts. Their reading comprehension and expanded vocabulary both result in a rise in their overall language proficiency.

Additionally, the curriculum enhances students' ability to think critically. As students deal with a variety of texts, they enhance their capacity to assess and examine information. They are requested to investigate their assumptions, consider a variety of perspectives, and formulate well-reasoned arguments. This ability to think critically goes beyond reading and helps students in numerous areas of their personal and academic lives.

Children who read a lot generally have richer experiences. Their horizons are expanded, their creativity develops, and empathy and comprehension are nurtured. Students gain the confidence to actively engage with ideas, participate in conversations, and express their unique views. One of the respondents says that:

"When I share what I have learned about the program with my fellow students, I will describe it through familiar words and explain to make it easy to understand. I will argue the importance of the program, the benefits that can be obtained and how it can help the development and success."

Nkomo (2021) provided evidence to support the previous claim by showing that students believed the extensive reading program (ERP) had enhanced their writing and reading skills, as well as their motivation, enthusiasm, and attitude towards reading. The study indicates that ERP can influence behavioral shifts, foster a love of reading, and increase learners' reading affective levels.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study sought to understand how the teachers of Landy National High School assessed the students during an extensive reading literacy program. The selected junior high students from Landy National High School were the participants of this study.

The importance and role of teachers in extensive reading are crucial for students' development and the acquisition of skills and knowledge. Four criteria can be used to categorize the significance of extensive reading: the influence of the reading program, teacher guidance, effective teaching, and the effect of the reading program. The table's data indicates that many respondents place a high value on their teachers' assistance since it supports their skill development and increases their understanding of extensive literacy. Reading comprehension is enhanced by teacher guidance, which also strengthens language proficiency and efficient communication. Giving students additional reading resources and regularly pushing them to read with the help of their teachers improves their reading abilities.

The challenges of extensive reading are classified into Guide, Progress, and Examine categories. The fact that respondents are actively aiming to manage their duties well highlights the significance of supervision for jobs requiring multitasking, such as being a student. They value the use of old notes and books as sources of information.

Nevertheless, because of their hectic schedules and small living spaces, they struggle to find an appropriate moment to read and write. This makes it difficult to provide a setting that encourages reading and supports students' learning objectives. The information in the table reveals that respondents place a high value on the advice given by teachers. The study underlines how a wide range of reading in the curriculum helps students develop their critical thinking abilities, their capacity to assess material from various perspectives, and their motivation to question assumptions and build persuasive arguments. Reading may broaden perspectives, improve experiences, foster empathy and understanding, develop imagination, and go beyond academic success. Additionally, it gives students the confidence to voice their opinions and participate in class arguments.

Overall, the study concludes that successful extended reading programs involve teachers giving children guidance and support in addition to giving them the opportunity to use a range of reading materials. Despite obstacles, responders and students embrace the advantages of in-depth reading and appreciate its influence on their academic and personal development.

After coming up with this study, the researcher recommended it to all teachers, students, parents, and future researchers who should comprehend that teachers play a big role in the student's learning capability, especially in extensive reading literacy.

1. For teachers, they should focus on the individual needs of the students in terms of reading literacy, and they must assess them and give their support to their students.
2. For students, increasing their understanding of this situation will improve their reading skills and practice not only in school but also in their home with the help of their parents.
3. For parents, at a very young age they must practice their child's reading skills so that they can develop as time passes and continue teaching them how to read so they can be good at it.
4. For future researchers, they might use the findings of this research as a reference for their own work related to this topic since this study highlights that the selected students had challenged themselves as students who practice extensive reading literacy.

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